

The Role of Indian Railways in Tourism Sector

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Abstract:- Tourism is one of the fast growing sectors in all over the world. Tourism is travel for pleasure, leisure and recreation. Tourism consists of five main components, namely attraction, accessibility, amenities, accommodation and activities. All components are very important for the tourism sector. Accessibility mode is very important in tourism. There are various modes of transportation in India for tourists. Among all railways, it is one of the preferred means of transport. It offers unique views of the picturesque landscape rarely seen by road or air. Indian Railways offer a series of rail package tour for tourist to promote tourism. Railways play an important role in promoting tourism in India.

Keywords:- Travel & tourism, Amenities, Accessibility, Tourism & leisure, Rail travel package, Irctc.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is traveling from home to an area or place for pleasure, leisure & recreation and returning back home. According to the United Nation World Tourism Organisation “Tourists are people who travel for leisure, recreation or business and other purposes not related to the pursuit of a remunerated activity and stay in places outside their usual resident or environment for no more than staying a consecutive year visited place.

Tourism Sector is one among the world largest industries with numerous international traveler arrivals. Nowadays tourism has become a posh activity encompassing variety of relationship and sectors. Tourism business cares with attracting individuals to a destination, transporting them there, Lodging, feeding and leisure activities entertaining, them and returning them to their usual place.

Tourism infrastructure is extremely a lot of necessary for the event of tourism. Tourism infrastructure consists of the essential needs and services required for the triple-crown operation of the tourism sector. a number of the essential ingredients of tourism infrastructure are transportation, accommodation, food, and beverages services. The supply of quality transport, clean hygienically food, accommodation, traveler amenities, guide services, searching and recreation of

tourists are some factors which gives the strength to the Tourism sector.

There are five major elements in tourism specifically the Attraction, Accessibility, Accommodation, Amenities, and Activities. Among all the components of tourism, Accessibility or transport is one among the key components of the tourism industry. Accessibility refers to the approach during which a traveler access to a destination. The way is also any variety of transport system. A.K. Raina in his book Tourism industry in Kashmir has aforementioned “Transport network is to tourism what veins are to the body system”. The age in transport system has brought a few boosts to the Tourism sector.

A tourist invariably needs a convenient, comfortable, low-cost and safe transport facility. Traveling by train is in an exceedingly one among one in every of the simplest choice for this. Not solely those, trains are fast, economical and spacious in contrast to craft and coaches. These will take sizable amount of individuals in a single trip. However, choosing mode of transport by the tourists depends on some factors like income, standing and cost.

Transport is one of the main complicated world economic sectors. It not only forms the backbone of national and international commerce by acting as a mechanism for the movement of people, however conjointly for business industry. Transport is considered united of the vital component of infrastructure for the expansion associate degreed development of any region because it provides the linkages. Transport is taken into account as an index of progress. Since tourism includes the motion of humans from their region of house to a vacationer vacation spot the courting among delivery and tourism improvement may be very crucial and strong. For the improvement of any vacation spot, good enough and green transportation is necessary.

Transport, consequently is one of the simple additives of tourism. Even alevn though rail journey is maximum handy and economical, but with the ultra-modern technological advances, the advent of pace automobiles and plane has decreased the passenger traffic for railways in lots of advanced nations. At the same time in nations like India, teach journey remains the maximum preferred mode of delivery.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- **Research Design:** Research design is a blueprint of a scientific study. It includes research methodologies, tools, and techniques to conduct the research. It helps to identify and address the problem that may rise during the process of research and analysis. There are many types of research design. Descriptive research design is used in this research.
- **Descriptive study:** A Descriptive Design seeks to describe the current status of a variable or phenomenon. The researcher does not begin with a hypothesis, but typically develops one after the data is collected. Data collection is mostly observational in nature.
- **Data Collection Source:** The study was conducted with secondary data which was collected from various websites, books, government sites, etc.
- **Methods of Data Collection:** Secondary data was collected from various websites, books, government sites, etc. based on the objectives and the variables that affect the study.

III. HISTORY OF INDIAN RAILWAY:

Indian railway is India's biggest country wide undertaking, and additionally biggest railway community of Asia. In India earlier than the first legitimate rail adventure, steamed locomotion changed into in operation from 1830 itself. In 1842, Charles Blacker Vignoles, Professor of Civil Engineering at the University of London, proposed in that railways are assembled in India. However, the legitimate opening of the first railway began in April, 1853, thanks to the efforts of Lord Dalhousie, Governor-General of British -India. Lord Dalhousie is considered to be the founder of the Indian railway system. It carried 400 people in 14 cars and ran from Bombay to Thane a distance of 32 km. The duration of this program has been changed to seventy-five minutes. After a multitude of applications were made for railroad production. Between 1853 and 1860 secured by cover by initially in the railways were operated by private organization. Between the years 1925 and 1950 took over the government of India. During the independence of India in 1947, the British colonial government advanced 54,000 km in of railways. Modern railroading is a fantastic integration of superior management and engineering prowess. Today it is by far the fourth largest railway community in the world.

➤ *Rail Tours in India:*

One of the satisfactory methods to peer India is thru the railways. Railways cowl maximum elements of India. It makes the traveler experience the lifestyle of India and now no longer handiest has that it given a clean image of the nation. Thus to sell tourism in India, the Indian Railways in collaboration with the State Tourism Development Corporations has added some of rail excursions for the home in addition to global vacationers. Some of them are,

➤ *Fairy Queen:*

This is the oldest operating Steam locomotive within side the world. It changed into constructed in 1855. It changed into overhauled in 1996 and resumed operations in 1997. It changed into licensed through the Guinness Book of World Records because the world's oldest operating locomotive.

➤ *Palace on Wheels:*

This changed into operated through the Rajasthan Tourism Development Corporation, in conjunction with the Indian Railways. It began out its operation in 1982 as unique history travelers teach for imparting a completely unique and noteworthy enjoy to the vacationers journeying India. Earlier the Palace on Wheels changed into constrained to overseas vacationers; however it changed into later opened to Indians too. It presents an adventure reminiscent to the royal kings. It takes the vacationers to experience the beauty of the Rajputs. The adventure starts from Delhi each Wednesday. Cultural suggests are organized at each halt of the train.

➤ *Royal Rajasthan on Wheels:*

It is a step beforehand of Palace on Wheels. Following the achievement of the Palace on Wheels the Rajasthan Tourism Development Corporation and the Indian Railway mutually released this train. It is extra costly than Palace on Wheels.

➤ *Royal Orient:*

These teach takes the vacationers to the captivating nation of Gujarat. It travels to palaces and forts. It is prepared with all current facilities. There are multi delicacies eating places and additionally a library.

➤ *Deccan Odyssey:*

The Maharashtra Tourism Development Corporation (MTDC) and Central Railway have promoted mutually a reproduction of palace on wheels with inside the call of, the Deccan Odyssey. The teach has presidential suites, forty eight deluxe suites, living room and convention cars, a uniqueness eating place and bar, tv and cable connections, fax machines, mobileular telephones on demand, forex facilities, laundry offerings, 24 hour room offerings and a valet. It offers an aristocratic tour enjoy. It travels in the course of the locations of Maharashtra.

➤ *Mahaparinirvana Express:*

As the call suggests, it's far a unique teach on a famous Buddhist circuit, operated through Indian Railways in affiliation with Indian Railway Catering and Tourism Corporation. It gives an all inclusive one week bundle overlaying predominant locations associated with the existence of Lord Buddha like Budhgaya, Rajgir, Nalanda, Varanasi, Sarnath, Kushinagar, Lumbini, Sravasti & Agra, with flexibility to regulate the applications in case of institution bookings. While the operation of the teach is undertaken through the Railways, the on-board / off-board

offerings, advertising, etc. is controlled through Indian Railways Catering and Tourism Corporation Ltd.

➤ *Bharat Darshan Train:*

The Bharat Darshan trains envisage taking some of vacationers from a selected location and taking them to traveller locations in different areas of the Country at a financial cost. The locations are in particular of historic, non secular and different tourism importance. The trains perform on some of exclusive itineraries throughout the country. The itinerary additionally continues on converting from time to time. The bundle consists of rail tour, street transfer, food, lodging in addition to sightseeing and is derived at an inexpensive cost. While the operation of the teach is undertaken through the Railways, the on-board / off-board offerings, ticketing, etc. is controlled through Indian Railways Catering and Tourism Corporation Ltd.

➤ *Irctc:*

The Indian Railways perform luxurious traveller trains in affiliation with Indian Railway tourism Catering Corporation or State Tourism Corporations. The predominant a part of operation and upkeep of the trains is undertaken through the Railways at the same time as the off-board / on-board offerings and advertising is carried out through the respective State Tourism Corporations.

➤ *Punjtakht Train:*

As an undertaking to facilitate rail tour to critical locations of Sikh pilgrimage, this teach connects the 5 takhs at Amritsar, AnadpurSaheb, Bhatinda, Nanded and Patna and gives all inclusive bundle overlaying teach adventure, lodging, nearby delivery food etc. at inexpensive rate. While the operation of the teach is undertaken through the Railways, the on-board / off-board offerings, ticketing, etc. is controlled through Indian Railway Catering and Tourism Corporation Ltd.

➤ *Steam Train:*

A Steam teaches among Delhi to Alwar and again performs fortnightly all through the iciness months. The operation of the teach is undertaken through the Railways; the on-board offerings, ticketing, etc. is controlled through Indian Railway Catering and Tourism Corporation and off-board offerings at Sariska is controlled through Rajasthan Tourism Development corporation.

➤ *Golden Chariot:*

This is operated through the Karnataka Tourism Development Corporation and the Southern Railways. It is the mind toddler of the Karnataka Tourism Development Corporation. It has eating places, bar, a compartment with spa and gym. It is a completely air conditioned luxurious teach with 11 residential coaches. To tour on this teach the traveller have a possibility to begin their adventure from Bangalore or Goa.

➤ *Hill Railways:*

Hill Railway refers to rail- traces connecting hill stations. It changed into first of all constructed through the British for the British settlers. Till 1920's there had been 4 such rail-traces constructed through exclusive organizations in 4 exclusive elements of British India. These four rail- traces had been Darjeeling Himalayan Railway, 1879, Nilgiri Railway 1899, Kalka Shimla Railway, 1903 and Matheran Light Railway, 1907. At gift which will entice the vacationers the authorities operates some of hill rails. Not handiest that there are toy trains that runs handiest in hill stations. These toy trains aren't rapid and that they run in a slim gauge. These trains provide the traveler a completely unique enjoy of viewing the mountain and the usa side.

➤ *Indrail Pass:*

This is geared toward imparting higher carrier to overseas vacationers. Foreign vacationers should purchase an Indrail Pass and tour in Indian trains. The idea changed into derived from the Eurail Pass. It allows limitless tour in India for a particular term from 1/2 of an afternoon to ninety days. Payment for the byskip needs to be made in US dollar, British Pound or different convertible overseas currencies. It is handiest to be had to Foreign Tourists, Indian Nationals dwelling overseas touring on legitimate passport, Indian partner of a overseas vacationers and a manual accompanying the overseas vacationers. In India, Indrail passes are to be had on the market in Tourist Bureaus at predominant Railway Stations. Recognized tour marketers in India and overseas also are approved to promote those passes in Delhi, Mumbai, Calcutta and Chennai and that they get a fee of 10 percent. These passes are to be had with a term of 7, 15, 21, 30, 60 and ninety days with exclusive tariffs. The Indrailbyskip is appealing even for the transit and quick live visitors. The passes at the moment are to be had for 1/2 of day, and 4 days for the power of such visitors.

IV. FINDING & DISCUSSION

The growth in FTAs in India during the eighties & nineties did not follow any consistent pattern. While the years, viz. 2003 to 2007, 2010, 2014 and 2017 saw double-digit positive growth, there was negative growth in the years 1991, 2001, 2002 and 2009. NRI arrivals have registered 1.4 % growth in 2018 over 2017. The International Tourist Arrivals in India has also registered positive annual growth of 11.8% and 3.7% in 2017 and 2018, respectively. The month-wise break up of NRIs arrival and International Tourist Arrivals in India during 2015 -2018 along with the growth rates are given in Table respectively.

Fig 1: International Tourist Arrival in INDIA
 Source: Bureau of Immigration, Govt. of India

Fig 2: Most States Visited by International Tourist
 Source: Ministry of tourism

V. CONCLUSION

Tourism in India is not possible without rail travel as it is a common form of public transport in the country. Trains are not only a cheaper and more reliable means of transport in India, but they also touch almost every major and minor tourist spot. They promote tourism by offering various promotional programs, travel packages, special trains, charter trains, luxury trains and coaches for domestic and foreign tourists. The tourism industry is not a single industry. It's an industry that spans many areas. These sectors play a crucial role and one of them is the transportation industry. Transportation is one of the essential parts of the tourism industry. Although there are different modes of transportation in India to see the beautiful tourist resources of the country, railway is one of the cheapest and most convenient means of transportation for people out there. Indian Railways is taking effective measures to attract tourists. Hence, it can be stated that the Indian Railways plays an important role in promoting tourism in the country. It makes the tourism industry one of the income generating industries for the Indian government.

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